

Research Article

Formulation And Evaluation Of Polyherbal Capsules For Anti-Inflammatory Herbs

Aparna V.^{1*}, Arya R.¹, Faseeha V. K.¹, Mariya James¹, Priya Abraham²

¹Bachelor of pharmacy, Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research, Trikaripur, Kasaragod, India

²Professor, Department of Pharmacognosy, Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research, Trikaripur, Kasaragod, India

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 28 Oct 2024

Keywords:

Clerodendrum infortunatum, Carica papaya, Heliotropium indicum, Ananas comosus, Polyherbal, Anti-inflammatory, HRBC Membrane stabilization

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.14001776

ABSTRACT

Herbal formulation is a consisting of one or more than one fresh herbs or processed herbs in a particular ratio and are used to diagnose, treat diseases. Herbal capsules are dietary supplements that contain powdered or concentrated herbal extract encased in a capsule. The aim of the present work is to reveal the pharmacognostic and phytochemical anti-inflammatory activity for the formulation and standardization of polyherbal capsule. The required materials were collected from Trikaripur, Kasargod and subjected to successive solvent extraction, later pharmacognostic studies like microscopic evaluation, ash value and extractive values were carried out. Then the anti-inflammatory activity of the powder is studied. Anti-inflammatory activity is evaluated by HRBC membrane stabilization method by using diclophenac as reference drug.

INTRODUCTION

Herbal medicines are those contain active ingredients from plant parts, such as leaves, roots, or flowers. Like conventional medicines herbal medicine has effect on body, and can be harmful if not used correctly.¹ Inflammation is a normal response of the body to protect the tissues from infection, injury or diseases. The response begins with the production and release of chemical agents from cells in infected, injured or diseased tissues.

The inflammatory response can either acute or chronic. Acute inflammation lasts only for few days. If the wound turns red, hot, hurts or swells. Inflammation is a beneficial process serving to immobilize the area of injury as the rest of the immune system mobilizes to heal. Chronic inflammation become problem when the solution to infection, injury or disease. Chronically inflamed tissues continue to generate signals that

*Corresponding Author: Aparna V.

Address: Bachelor of pharmacy, Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research, Trikaripur, Kasaragod, India

Email ✉: aparnaabu2001@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

attract leukocytes from the bloodstream.² The present work is to develop polyherbal capsule containing phytopharmaceuticals applied in the treatment of inflammation. Polyherbal formulations are effective for anti-inflammatory process. They can stimulate a variety of physiological functions that accelerates the process of inflammatory action. Papaya is an herbaceous perennial plant usually has a single, semi woody, hollow, erect stem, which terminates with a cluster of large, palmately lobed leaves with long petioles and latex vessels in all tissues. A crown shaped leaves are found in spiral manner, palmate lobes, and each lobe again pinnately lobed. Leaves are dark green colored. It also contains active constituents like saponin, flavonoids, flavones, steroids, tannins, glycosides, reducing sugars. It has Anti-inflammatory action, improve blood sugar control, support skin and hair health, prevent cancer.³ The Hill Glory Bower is a flowering, semi-herbaceous, and gregarious shrub, which naturally forms groups around the parent plant. These are erect, quadrangular branches covered with a dense, short layer of yellow hairs. It contains active ingredients such as Clerodolone, Clerodone, Clerodol, and a steroid named Clerosterol, glycosides, alkaloids, terpenoids, tannins. Antimicrobial, anthelmintic, hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anticonvulsant activity.⁴ Heliotropium indicum is an erect, thick fetid, annual or perennial herb with hirsute ascending branches. The leaves are opposite or sub-opposite, alternate or sub-alternate and straight forward, sheet-shaped from ovate to elliptical, hairy, and sharp. The margins of the leaves are undulate; the nerves present on both sides are serrulate or cordate and clearly visible under the leaves. It contains active constituents like alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, glycosides, oils, steroids. It has wound healing, anti-inflammatory, anti-dote, cure eye infection, antiseptic, treat kidney problem.⁶ Pineapple leaves

considered an herbaceous, tropical, and monocot perennial plant. Its leaves are spiral in arrangement and on the terminal ends have flowers which then produce edible fruit. It contains active constituents such as alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, glycosides. It helps to fight cough and cold, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant activity, monitor nervous system function.⁵

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of plant material

The fresh leaves of Clerodendrom infortunatum, Carica papaya, Heliotropium indicum, Ananas comosus were collected from Kasargod and Kozhikode district, Kerala(India) in the month of April 2024.

Authentication of plant material

The plant material was collected from Kasaragod and Kozhikode district, Kerala(India) in the month of April 2024. The plant material was identified and authenticated by Dr.K.M. Sreekumar, Professor (Entomology) College of Agriculture Kerala, Agricultural University, Padanakkad, Kasargod District, Kerala.

Extraction of plant material

Extraction of leaves of Clerodendrum infortunatum, Caricapapaya, Heliotropium indicum, Ananas comosus was carried out by using maceration method. Heliotropium indicum was washed and shade dried. For maceration the dried plant material was macerated in 95% Ethanol for 3 days, filtered and dried to obtain ethanolic extract. Caricapapaya was washed and dried. For maceration the dried plant material was macerated in methanol for 24 hours and filtered and dried to obtain methanolic extract. Ananas comosus was washed, dried and powdered. The powdered plant material was macerated in methanol for 72 hours, filtered and dried to obtain extract. Clerodendrom infortunatum was washed and dried. The extract sample was soaked in 200ml of methanol for 32 hours and filtered and dried to obtain the extract.

Preliminary phytochemical screening The extracts of selected plants were subjected to phytochemical screening to detect the various phytoconstituents present such as alkaloids, carbohydrate, proteins, glycosides, tannins, saponins, flavonoids, terpenoids, steroids, amino acids, phytosterols

Formulation of polyherbal capsule

SI No.	INGREDIENTS	QUANTITY (mg)		
		Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3
1.	Powdered plant material	400	400	400
2.	Talc	10	11	15
3.	MCC	10	12	14
4.	Magnesium stearate	18.5	14	12.5
5.	Colloidal silicon dioxide	11	12	10
6.	Methyl paraben	0.5	0.4	0.5

Powdered mixture along with other excipients were weighed and pass through the sieve no.44. The Pre-formulation studies were carried out. Three trials were conducted and most suitable is selected (trial 3). "0" size capsule shells were de dusted transferred into polybags and filled by using hand operated gelatin capsule filling machine to an average net content of weight.7-8

Physical characteristics

Bulk density, angle of repose, Hausner's ratio, Carr's index, and particle size distribution was determines for

evaluating the physical characteristics of the powder.⁹

A. Bulk Density
10g of powder mixture was taken in a graduated measuring cylinder on a wooden surface. Bulk density is calculated using formulated.

B. Angle of repose

It was determined by using funnel method. The powder was allowed to flow through a funnel fixed on a stand to form a heap.

C. Compressibility /Carr's index

This is calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Carr's index} = \frac{(\text{Tapped density} - \text{Bulk tapped density})}{\text{Tapped density}} \times 100$$

D. Hausner's ratio

The formula used to determine the Hausner's ratio is:

$$\text{Hausner's ratio} = \frac{\text{Tapped density}}{\text{Bulk density}}$$

INVITRO ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY

The HRBC membrane stabilization was used as a method to evaluate the anti-inflammatory activity.

The collected blood was mixed with an equal volume of sterilized Alsever medium (2% w/v dextrose, 0.8% sodium citrate, 0.5% citric acid and 0.42% sodium chloride in water). The blood was further centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 min and the packed cells were washed with isosaline (0.85% pH 7.2) and finally 10% v/v suspension was made with isosaline. The assay mixture contained the secondary metabolite from the plant extract, 1 ml phosphate buffer (0.15 M pH 7.4), 2 ml hypo saline (0.36%) and 0.5 ml HRBC suspension. Diclophenac was used as a referenced drug. 2 ml distilled water was used as the control. The assay mixture was incubated at 37°C for 30 min and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 min. The hemoglobin content in the supernatant was estimated using a UV - Visible spectrophotometer at 560 nm,

$$\text{The percentage of hemolysis} = \frac{(\text{OD of test solution} / \text{OD of control}) \times 100}{\text{OD} = \text{Optical density}}$$

Anti-inflammatory activity is percent of protection is calculated using the formula,

$$\text{Percent of protection} = 100 - \text{Hemolytic percentage}$$

“OD of test” is optical density or the test sample’s absorbance and “OD of control” is optical density or absorbance of negative control.¹⁰

EVALUATION OF POLYHERBAL CAPSULE¹¹

a. Weight variation test

The variability in the amount of powder contained in each herbal capsule was measured by the weight variation test. Twenty herbal capsules were randomly selected and weighed. Then the average weight is calculated and compared with the individual herbal capsule weight. The percentage variation was calculated as per USP (2010) specifications. The herbal capsule shell is not less than 90% and not more than 110% of theoretically calculated weight of each unit.

b. Disintegration Test

The disintegration test is the measure of the time required under a given set of conditions in which the selected capsule was disintegrated into the particles that pass through 10 mesh screens within a specified time.

c. Determination of Moisture content

The loss on the drying test is important when the herbal substance is known to be hygroscopic. An excess of water in medicinal plant material will encourage microbial growth, the presence of fungi, and insect Deterioration. In modern pharmaceutical technology, the moisture content provides information concerning The shelf life and quality of the drug.

$$\text{Moisture content (\%)} = \left(\frac{\text{Final weight of sample}}{\text{initial weight of sample}} \right) \times 100$$

d. Determination of pH

1g of capsule powder was taken and dissolved in 100ml demineralized water. The pH value of the solution was determined by a digital pH meter. The pH meter was calibrated using a buffer of 4.9 and 7 pH. The electrodes were immersed in the test solution and pH was measured.

RESULTS

Preliminary phytochemical screening

The crude drugs with solvents like water, methanol, ethanol and they were subjected to preliminary phytochemical screening to detect the phytochemical constituents.

SI No.	Chemical constituents	Clerodendrum infortunatum	Caricapapaya	Heliotropium indicum	Ananas comosus
1.	Alkaloids	+	+	+	+
2.	Carbohydrates	+	+	-	-
3.	Flavonoids	-	+	+	+
4.	Glycosides	-	-	-	+
5.	Tannins	+	+	-	+
6.	Proteins	-	+	-	-
7.	Steroids	-	+	-	-
8.	Terpenoids	+	-	-	-
9.	Amino acids	-	+	-	-
10.	Phytosterols	+	+	-	-
11.	Saponins	-	+	+	-

Evaluation of poly herbal capsule

After filling of powder mixture the capsule is evaluated for weight variation among the capsule, moisture content, disintegration testing and pH of 1% aqueous solution is determined.

Name of the test	Observation
Weight variation	461mg±2.3mg
Moisture content	3.7%±0.22%
Disintegration	6.55±0.32min
pH	7.33±0.21

Invitro anti- inflammatory activity by HRBC Membrane stabilization method

The HRBC membrane stabilization was used to evaluate the anti -inflammatory activity. It is done by using collected goat blood and mixed with

Alsever medium prepared. Anti-inflammatory activity is determined by HRBC method to determined the percentage prevention of Hemolysis.

Concentration	Absorbance	Prevention of lysis(%)
300	0.175	27.68±0.06
200	0.183	24.38±0.67
100	0.195	19.42±0.77
Diclofenac	0.127	47.36
Negative control	0.242	0

Prevention of lysis (%) v/s concentration graph

DISCUSSION

The formulated poly herbal capsule contains Clerodendrum infortunatum, Heliotropium indicum, Ananas comosus, Carica papaya .which are collected from Trikaripur, washed and dried under shade and powdered. The capsule consisting of fine powder of herbs in appropriate ratio was subjected to standardization by means of various physical and chemical methods. The pH was determined to avoid gastric irritation and the moisture content was determined to find out any increase in weight caused by moisture absorption. The value obtained was found to be within the standard. The Anti-inflammatory activity was conducted by using Human Red Blood Cell(HRBC) membrane stabilization assay and the result shows Anti-inflammatory activity.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This thesis has been kept on tract and seen through to completion with the support and encouragement

of numerous people. It is delightful moment for us to express our heartfelt gratitude and sincere thanks to our esteemed guide Mrs. Priya Abraham, Professor, Department of pharmacognosy, Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Pharmaceutical science and research, for her constant guidance, valuable suggestion and encouragement. We would also like to say thanks to all the non-teaching staff and library staff for their help in the completion of study.

REFERENCES

1. Subramani P ,Gani ST, Sokkalingam A, Dhanaraj. Polyherbal formulation: Concept of Ayurf=veda . *Pharmac Rev.*2014;8(16):73-80.
2. Maithani Jyoti, Agarwal Kshitij, Sharma Vivek, Saini Prem, Preparation and standardization of a polyherbal formulation. *Journal of Advanced scientific research.*2012;3(2):110-113.

3. Jitpisute Chunthorn-Orn, Bhanuz Dechayont, Pathompong Phuaklee et al., Cytotoxic, Anti-inflammatory and antioxidant activities of *Heliotropium indicum* extracts, *J Med Assoc Thai*, Vol 99 suppl.4, 2016.
4. Laila Kamilla, Sri Tumpuk, Maulidiyah Salim, Anti-inflammatory of Papaya leaf extract towards membrane stabilization of Red blood cells, *Journal Kesehatan Prima* (2021), 15 (1).
5. Sucheta Mondal, Sanjib Battacharya, Evaluation of acute anti-inflammatory effect of *Ananas comosus* leaf extracts in rats, *Pharmacologyonline*, 2011, 1312-1315.
6. Dr. Rimjhim Sheel, Kumari Nisha, Prof. Jainendra Kumar, Preliminary Phytochemical screening of Methanolic extract of *Clerodendrum infortunatum*, *IOSR Journal of Applied Chemistry*, (2014), 7(1) Ver II, 10-13.
7. Shinde JS, Khurde SS, Suchita LS, Chanvan SS, Hulmajge SB. Need of polyherbal formulation and its standardization: A Review. *World J Pharm pharmac Scien*. 2016; 5(11) 526-533.
8. Malarvizhi R, Abhishek P, Barathidasan, Potential wound healing properties of a polyherbal formulation in an experimental model on wistar rats. *Biomedicine*. 2020; 39(1) : 40-51.
9. Umme Seema N, SL Jagadeesh, Chandrashekar VM et al., Development and evaluation of the physical properties of polyherbal formulations for antiobesity, *The Pharma innovation journal*, 2022; 11(11) : 1409-1412.
10. Amin Chowdhury, Shofiul Azam et al., Antibacterial activities and in vitro anti-inflammatory (Membrane stability) properties of methanolic extracts of *Gardenia coronaria* leaves, *IJM*, Vol 2014 issue 1.

HOW TO CITE: Aparna V., Arya R., Faseeha V. K., Mariya James, Priya Abraham, Formulation And Evaluation Of Polyherbal Capsules For Anti-Inflammatory Herbs, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 10, 1676-1681. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14001776>

